

ENSURING SECURE AND SPACE-EFFICIENT METADATA MANAGEMENT IN ENCRYPTED DEDUPLICATION

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ABSTRACT

Encrypted deduplication combines encryption and deduplication in a seamless way to provide confidentiality guarantees for the physical data in deduplicated storage, yet it incurs substantial metadata storage overhead due to the additional storage of keys. We present a new encrypted deduplication storage system called Metadedup, which suppresses metadata storage by also applying deduplication to metadata. Its idea builds on indirection, which adds another level of metadata chunks that record metadata information. We find that metadata chunks are highly redundant in real-world workloads and hence can be effectively deduplicated. We further extend Metadedup to incorporate multiple servers via a distributed key management approach, so as to provide both fault-tolerant storage and security guarantees. We extensively evaluate Metadedup from performance and storage efficiency perspectives. We show that Metadedup achieves high throughput in writing and restoring files, and saves the metadata storage by up to 93.94% for real-world backup workloads.

1. INTRODUCTION

Chunk-based deduplication is widely used in modern primary [31] and backup [26], [39], [42] storage systems to achieve high storage savings. It stores only a

single physical copy of duplicate chunks, while referencing all duplicate chunks to the physical copy by small-size references. Prior studies show that deduplication can effectively reduce the storage space of primary storage by 50% [31] and that of backup storage by up to 98% [39]. This motivates the wide deployment of deduplication in various commercial cloud storage services (e.g., Dropbox, Google Drive, Bitcasa, Mozy, and Memopal) to reduce substantial storage costs [18].

To provide confidentiality guarantees, encrypted deduplication [7], [8] adds an encryption layer to deduplication, such that each chunk, before being written to deduplicated storage, is deterministically encrypted via symmetric-key encryption by a key derived from the chunk content (e.g., the key is set to be the cryptographic hash of chunk content [14]). This ensures that duplicate chunks have identical content even after encryption, and hence we can still apply deduplication to the encrypted chunks for storage savings. Many studies (e.g., [5], [7], [25], [33], [36]) have designed various encrypted deduplication schemes to efficiently manage outsourced data in cloud storage.

In addition to storing non-duplicate data, a deduplicated storage system needs to keep

de duplication metadata. There are two types of de duplication metadata. To check if identical chunks exist, the system maintains a fingerprint index that tracks the fingerprints of all chunks that have already been stored. Also, to allow a file to be reconstructed, the system maintains a file recipe that holds the mappings from the chunks in the file to the references of the corresponding physical copies.

De duplication metadata is notoriously known to incur high storage overhead [11], [21], [30], especially for the highly redundant workloads (e.g., backups) as the metadata storage overhead becomes more dominant. In this work, we argue that encrypted de duplication incurs even higher metadata storage overhead, as it additionally keeps key metadata, such as the key recipes that track the chunk-to-key mappings to allow the decryption of individual files. Since the key recipes contain sensitive key information, they need to be managed separately from file recipes, encrypted by the master keys of file owners, and individually stored for different file owners. Such high metadata storage overhead can negate the storage effectiveness of encrypted de duplication in real deployment.

Contributions. To address the storage overhead of both de duplication metadata and key metadata, we design and implement Metadedup, a new encrypted de duplication system that effectively suppresses metadata storage. Our contributions are summarized as follows.

- _ Metadedup builds on the idea of indirection. Instead of directly storing all de duplication and key metadata in both file

and key recipes (both of which dominate the metadata storage overhead), we group the metadata in the form of meta data chunks that are stored in encrypted deduplication storage. Thus, both file and key recipes now store references to metadata chunks, which now contain references to data chunks (i.e., the chunks of file data). If Metadedup stores nearly identical files regularly (e.g., periodic backups [39]), the corresponding file and key metadata are expected to have long sequences of references that are in the same order. This implies that the metadata chunks are highly redundant and hence can be effectively de duplicated.

- _ We propose a distributed key management approach that adapts Metadedup into a multi-server architecture for fault tolerant data storage. We generate the key of each data chunk from one of the servers, encode it via secret sharing and distribute the resulting shares to remaining servers. This ensures fault-tolerant storage of data chunks, while being robust against adversarial compromise on a number of servers through our decoupled management of keys and shares.

- _ We implement a Metadedup prototype and evaluate its performance in a networked setup. Compared to the network speed of our Gigabit LAN test bed, we show that Metadedup incurs only 13.09% and 3.06% of throughput loss in writing and restoring files, respectively.

- _ Finally, we conduct trace-driven simulation on two realworld datasets. We show that Metadedup achieves up to 93.94% of metadata storage savings in encrypted deduplication. We also show that

Metadedup maintains the storage load balance among all servers.

The rest of this paper proceeds as follows. Section 2 motivates the need of mitigating metadata storage overhead in encrypted de duplication via mathematical analysis and trace-driven simulation. Section 3 reviews related work. Section 4 presents the design of Metadedup. Section 5 extends Metadedup with distributed key management. Section 6 presents the implementation details of our Metadedup prototype. Section 7 presents our evaluation results. Finally, Section 8 concludes this paper. In the digital supplementary file, we present security analysis on Metadedup and additional evaluation results on the storage usage of Metadedup.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

"Transparent data deduplication in the cloud"

Cloud storage providers such as Dropbox and Google drive heavily rely on data deduplication to save storage costs by only storing one copy of each uploaded file. Although recent studies report that whole file deduplication can achieve up to 50% storage reduction, users do not directly benefit from these savings-as there is no transparent relation between effective storage costs and the prices offered to the users. In this paper, we propose a novel storage solution, ClearBox, which allows a storage service provider to transparently attest to its customers the deduplication patterns of the (encrypted) data that it is storing. By doing so, ClearBox enables cloud users to verify the effective storage

space that their data is occupying in the cloud, and consequently to check whether they qualify for benefits such as price reductions, etc. ClearBox is secure against malicious users and a rational storage provider, and ensures that files can only be accessed by their legitimate owners. We evaluate a prototype implementation of ClearBox using both Amazon S3 and Dropbox as back-end cloud storage. Our findings show that our solution works with the APIs provided by existing service providers without any modifications and achieves comparable performance to existing solutions.

"Provable data possession at untrusted stores",

We introduce a model for provable data possession (PDP) that allows a client that has stored data at an untrusted server to verify that the server possesses the original data without retrieving it. The model generates probabilistic proofs of possession by sampling random sets of blocks from the server, which drastically reduces I/O costs. The client maintains a constant amount of metadata to verify the proof. The challenge/response protocol transmits a small, constant amount of data, which minimizes network communication. Thus, the PDP model for remote data checking supports large data sets in widely-distributed storage system.

We present two provably-secure PDP schemes that are more efficient than previous solutions, even when compared with schemes that achieve weaker guarantees. In particular, the overhead at the server is low (or even constant), as opposed to linear in the size of the data. Experiments

using our implementation verify the practicality of PDP and reveal that the performance of PDP is bounded by disk I/O and not by cryptographic computation.

"DupLESS: Server-aided encryption for deduplicated storage"

Cloud storage service providers such as Dropbox, Mozy, and others perform deduplication to save space by only storing one copy of each file uploaded. Should clients conventionally encrypt their files, however, savings are lost. Message-locked encryption (the most prominent manifestation of which is convergent encryption) resolves this tension. However it is inherently subject to brute-force attacks that can recover files falling into a known set. We propose an architecture that provides secure deduplicated storage resisting brute-force attacks, and realize it in a system called DupLESS. In DupLESS, clients encrypt under message-based keys obtained from a key-server via an oblivious PRF protocol. It enables clients to store encrypted data with an existing service, have the service perform deduplication on their behalf, and yet achieves strong confidentiality guarantees. We show that encryption for deduplicated storage can achieve performance and space savings close to that of using the storage service with plaintext data.

"Message-locked encryption and secure deduplication"

We formalize a new cryptographic primitive that we call Message-Locked Encryption (MLE), where the key under which encryption and decryption are performed is itself derived from the message. MLE

provides a way to achieve secure deduplication (space-efficient secure outsourced storage), a goal currently targeted by numerous cloudstorage providers. We provide definitions both for privacy and for a form of integrity that we call tag consistency. Based on this foundation, we make both practical and theoretical contributions. On the practical side, we provide ROM security analyses of a natural family of MLE schemes that includes deployed schemes. On the theoretical side the challenge is standard model solutions, and we make connections with deterministic encryption, hash functions secure on correlated inputs and the sample-then-extract paradigm to deliver schemes under different assumptions and for different classes of message sources. Our work shows that MLE is a primitive of both practical and theoretical interest.

3. EXISTING SYSTEM

Mandal et al. [29] transfer application metadata to block-layer deduplication, so as to accelerate the deduplication speed. Lin et al. [27] separate metadata from data to improve the storage efficiency of deduplication. While the above studies address metadata management, they do not consider how to mitigate metadata storage overhead in deduplication.

Compression. Meister et al. [30] propose four approaches to replace the fingerprints in file recipes by short code words, so as to compress deduplication metadata (see Section 7.2 for details). However, they either cannot apply to the key recipe that is

encrypted by the file owner's master key, or only reduce the metadata of zero chunks.

– **Key reduction.** Dekey [22] applies deduplication to the keys directly to reduce the amount of key metadata. However, since the size of a key is often comparable to the size of the additional reference (both are of tens of bytes) to the corresponding physical copy, the storage saving of key metadata can be negated by such additional deduplication metadata in key-based deduplication. SecDep [41] and REED [33] generate one MLE key for a group of chunks to reduce the total number of keys. However, since duplicate chunks are possibly encrypted with different keys (i.e., the resulting encrypted chunks become different and cannot be deduplicated), these systems [33], [41] degrade the storage efficiency achieved by deduplication.

Disadvantages

- Metadep is not designed for an organization that outsources the storage of users' data to a remote shared storage system.
- There is less efficiency on the cloud data due to High storage overhead of metadata.

4. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Metadep builds on the idea of indirection. Instead of directly storing all deduplication and key metadata in both file and key recipes (both of which dominate the metadata storage overhead), we group the metadata in the form of metadata chunks that are stored in encrypted deduplication storage. Thus, both file and key recipes now

store references to metadata chunks, which now contain references to data chunks (i.e., the chunks of file data). If Metadep stores nearly identical files regularly (e.g., periodic backups [39]), the corresponding file and key metadata are expected to have long sequences of references that are in the same order. This implies that the metadata chunks are highly redundant and hence can be effectively deduplicated.

The system proposes a distributed key management approach that adapts Metadep into a multi-server architecture for fault tolerant data storage. We generate the key of each data chunk from one of the servers, encode it via secret sharing, and distribute the resulting shares to remaining servers. This ensures fault-tolerant storage of data chunks, while being robust against adversarial compromise on a number of servers through our decoupled management of keys and shares.

The system implements a Metadep prototype and evaluate its performance in a networked setup. Compared to the network speed of our Gigabit LAN testbed, we show that Metadep incurs only 13.09% and 3.06% of throughput loss in writing and restoring files, respectively.

Finally, the system conducts trace-driven simulation on two realworld datasets. We show that Metadep achieves up to 93.94% of metadata storage savings in encrypted deduplication. We also show that Metadep maintains the storage load balance among all servers.

Advantages

- The system ensures that our Meta dedup design is compatible with existing counter measures that address different threats against encrypted deduplication systems.
- A malicious client may abuse client-side deduplication to learn whether other users have already stored certain files, and Metadedup can defeat the side channel leakage by adopting the server-side deduplication on cross-user data. A malicious server may modify or even delete stored files to destroy the availability of outsourced files, and Metadedup is compatible with the availability countermeasure that disperses data across servers via deduplication-aware secret sharing.

5. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

6. IMPLEMENTATION

• Data Owner Module

In this module, the data owner uploads their data in the cloud server. For the security purpose the data owner encrypts the data file’s blocks and then store in the cloud. The data owner can check the duplication of the file’s blocks over Corresponding cloud server. The Data owner can have capable of manipulating the encrypted data file’s blocks and the data owner can check the cloud data as well as the duplication of the specific file’s blocks and also he can create remote user with respect to registered cloud servers. The data owner also checks data integrity proof on which the block is modified by the attacker.

• Cloud Server Module

The cloud service provider manages a cloud to provide data storage service. Data owners encrypt their data file’s blockss and store them in the cloud for sharing with Remote User. To access the shared data file’s blockss, data consumers download encrypted data file’s blockss of their interest from the cloud and then decrypt them.

• End User

In this module, remote user logs in by using his user name and password. After he will request for secrete key of required file’s blocks from cloud servers, and get the secrete key. After getting secrete key he is trying to download file’s blocks by entering file’s blocks name and secrete key from cloud server.

- **Data Encryption and Decryption**

All the legal users in the system can freely query any interested encrypted and decrypted data. Upon receiving the data from the server, the user runs the decryption algorithm Decrypt to decrypt the cipher text by using its secret keys from different Users. Only the attributes the user possesses satisfy the access structure defined in the cipher text CT, the user can get the content key.

- **Attacker Module**

The user who attacks or modifies the block content called attacker. The attacker may be the user who tries to access the file contents by using wrong secret key from the cloud server.

7. CONCLUSION

We present Metadedup, which exploits the power of indirection to realize deduplication to metadata. It significantly mitigates the metadata storage overhead in encrypted deduplication, while preserving confidentiality guarantees for both data and metadata. We extend Metadedup for secure and fault-tolerant storage in a multi-server architecture; in particular, we propose a distributed key management approach, which preserves security guarantees even if a number of servers are compromised. We extensively evaluate Metadedup from performance and storage efficiency aspects. We show that Metadedup significantly suppresses the storage space of metadata, while incurring limited performance overhead compared to network speed.

FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

Integrating advanced cryptographic techniques like homomorphic encryption and zero-knowledge proofs can bolster security by enabling operations on encrypted data without compromising confidentiality. Embracing blockchain technology can introduce immutability and decentralization to metadata transactions, ensuring data integrity and accountability. Furthermore, the adoption of quantum-secure cryptography and secure hardware enclaves fortifies the system against emerging threats. Dynamic metadata partitioning, differential privacy techniques, and machine learning-based anomaly detection contribute to optimizing space utilization while safeguarding privacy and detecting potential security breaches. By embracing these advancements, encrypted deduplication systems can evolve to meet the escalating demands of data privacy and security in an increasingly interconnected digital landscape.

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